

Countertransference Among Nursing Students

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Abstract

Clinical experience had become a way of life among student nurses. Rendering therapeutic care is of major importance during patient care. To be able to provide the necessary care for clients they need to break the walls of unfamiliarity between them by establishing rapport that eventually will yield to effective communication and therapeutic use of self. This phenomenological study explored the lived experience of counter-transference among nursing students. Ten key informants were taken using purposive sampling and were interviewed using a content validated interview guide. Advantages and disadvantages were identified as a result of the counter-transference experience. Being able to help and enhance care towards the patient, being out of control over one's feelings, and being treated unprofessionally were the major themes that emerged. Since counter-transference was strongly viewed as going beyond the limitations, recommendation to student nurses were addressed to such boundary issues. This is to prevent, minimize, or eliminate possible conflicts on nurse-patient relationships.

Introduction

Faced with unique individuals, a nurse's professionalism may be put to test. One great challenge faced by nurses and nursing students is keeping the line between the nurse and the client relationship intact. "How does a client know when he has crossed the boundaries of the nurse-client relationship?" is exactly the same question that nurses have to deal with. Transference by clients and counter-transference by nurses is not an unfamiliar event or even far from being experienced as nurses are forced to deal with different clients everyday. And if nurse do experience this phenomenon, will it be destructive or beneficial to the nurse-client relationship?

Counter-transference has been defined by Boelcke (n.d.) as referring to how a nurse's feeling toward a client is altered when the client reminds the nurse of someone he or she knows or knew. The nurse may develop personal feelings, such as attraction or hatred, toward the client due to those associations between the client and the person that the clinician knew or knows. Those feelings, while often discussed in their more negative connotations, can also have a positive impact on the therapy.

Looking back at the history of the self-awareness program of the university, way back in 2005, the Gestalt Therapy Technique was a major tool utilized by the clinical instructors to develop self-awareness among students and help them best prepare for their clinical exposure. One of the main objectives of developing self-awareness was to prevent counter-transference. In 2008, where the number of students became unstopably high, where it reached to 32 sections with 50 students in each class, the Gestalt Therapy Technique was no longer feasible. There were only five available psychiatric nursing professors and only two are capable of handling the therapy while the rest acted as assistants only. Eventually, the self-awareness was transformed as a simple and plain classroom activity which is far beyond from the original Gestalt Therapy Technique. It was later on observed a year after that counter-transference issues emerged among students which triggers the conduct of the study. It is also the intent of the study to document the emerging phenomenon of counter-transference among students.

Theoretical Framework

Hildegard Peplau (1952) developed a model of nurse-client relationship or nurse patient interaction which has proved of great use to later nurse theorists and clinicians in developing more sophisticated

and therapeutic nursing interventions. Peplau identified six nursing roles to illustrate the dynamic character to clinical nursing: (1) accepting stranger that builds trust; (2) resource person; (3) teacher; (4) counselor; (5) surrogate; and (6) active leader and (7) technical expert. Within which developed within the stages of the Nurse-Client Relationship.

The interaction between client and nurse consists of four overlapping phases: (1) orientation; (2) identification; (3) exploitation; and (4) resolution. The mentioned phases sometimes overlap though they may appear in order. During the orientation phase, the nurse and client get to know each other and deal with any differences which include culture and educational attainment. During the identification phase, the main focus of the nurse is on discovering and understanding the health problem of the client. During the exploitation phase, the nurse uses all available resources and the facility in general, to address the problem. Lastly, during the resolution phase, the nurse works to resolve the health problem for the client. Since nursing involves interaction between two or more individuals with a common goal, then it is an interpersonal process. When the nurse has self-awareness, she notes her own patterns of behavior, acts to resolve interpersonal problems, and better interacts with the client. She will also be able to provide therapy and education, and improve the results of the client's care (Forchuk & Ward-Griffin, 2006; McNaughton, 2005; Peplau, 1952; Wiesman, 1992).

Peplau's theory focuses on the interpersonal processes and therapeutic relationship that nurse and client develops. The interpersonal focus requires that the nurse attends to the interpersonal processes that occur between the nurse and client. Interpersonal processes include the nurse-client relationship, communication, pattern integration and the roles of the nurse. According to Peplau (1952), psychodynamic nursing is being able to understand one's own behavior to be able to help others identify felt difficulties or problems and to apply the principles of human relations to the problems that arise at all levels of experience. Peplau's theory stressed the importance of the ability of the nurses to understand own behavior to help others identify perceived difficulties or problems.

Two common circumstances were identified by Pilette and associates (1995) which can lead to the smudging of boundaries. First is when the relationship slips into a social context and second is when the nurse's needs are met at the expense of the client's needs. Transference is the process whereby a person unconsciously and inappropriately displaces (transfers) onto individuals in his or her current life those patterns of behavior and emotional reactions that originated in relation to significant figures in childhood. While counter-transference on the other hand refers to the tendency of the nurse to displace or transfer onto the client feelings related to people in the nurse's past. In most cases, the client's transference to the nurse leads counter-transference feelings in the nurse.

According to Varcolis & Halter (2009), if the nurse feels either a strongly positive or a strongly negative reaction to a client, this could be a sign that the nurse is experiencing counter-transference. The nurse may have unnoticeable over recognition and identification with the client. When the nurse is confronted with such situation, the nurse may have difficulty identifying or even understanding the problems of the client which are similar to the nurse's problems.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to gain understanding of the experience of counter-transference among Level IV student nurses of the University of the Visayas.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following queries: (1) How did the counter-transference experienced by the informants; and (2) What was the meaning of counter-transference experienced by the informants?

Methodology

This study utilized the qualitative phenomenological method. This is to describe the lived experience of counter-transference among student nurses of University of the Visayas, Banilad, Cebu City.

Informants and Sampling. Ten (10) nursing students were purposively taken to be key informants of the study. They were senior students of the University of the Visayas College of Nursing who: (1) were exposed in the psychiatric wards; and (2) had experienced counter-transference with their clients.

Instruments. Schedule interview guides aided multiple unstructured key informant interviews. Observations confirmed results from interview. Different triangulation strategies were observed to derive authentic and credible data.

Data Analysis. Collaizzi's (1978 as cited by Polit & Beck, 2008) seven steps method was utilized: (1) each informant's verbatim transcript was read to acquire a sense of the whole; (2) significant statements and phrases pertaining to the phenomenon were extracted from each transcripts; (3) meanings were formulated from the significant statements; (4) meanings were organized into themes; (5) these results are integrated into a rich and exhaustive description of the lived experience; (6) essential structure of the phenomenon were formulated; and (7) validation was sought from the research informants to compare researcher's descriptive results with the lived experience. Modification to achieve congruence with the lived experience was observed.

Results

Counter-transference was observed to occur among students exposed in the psychiatric ward. The following themes about counter-transference emerged: (1) sense of closeness and intimacy; (2) unconscious phenomenon; (3) concern, pity and sympathy; (4) hostility; (5) charity and altruism; (6) appalling interest; and (7) ambivalence.

Sense of Closeness and Intimacy. Some informants reported that they experience extreme sense of closeness and intimacy. They treat their patients like a: (1) close relative; (2) parent; (3) dating partner; (4) close friend; and (5) older or younger sibling.

"It is the nurse's responsibility to establish and maintain a professional relationship with clients. When a nurse knows a client through a personal relationship, it may be difficult to maintain sufficient objectivity about the person to enable the nurse to enter into a professional relationship. Caution is required. Nurses need to be direct and explicit with clients, potential clients and former clients about the nature of their relationship. Difficulties arise when there is a lack of clarity about when the relationship is personal and when it is professional. Nurses who themselves are vulnerable because of difficult circumstances in their own life need to be particularly self-aware and thoughtful about maintaining professional boundaries in the nurse-client relationship." (College of Registered Nurses in British Columbia, 2006)

Unconscious Phenomenon. Notably, there are three informants who expressed no clear definition of the phenomenon. To the informants the experience of counter-transference tends to just happen spontaneously without having knowledge that they are into it already. They just felt that they have done "too much" for their patients.

According to O'Kelly (1998) countertransference is a psychoanalytical concept which, when applied to nursing, refers to the unconscious response of the nurse to the patient. Hilz (1996) claimed that unresolved conflicts from the nurse's past may evolve as countertransference and they may be completely unaware or only minimally aware of it as it is occurring.

Concern, Pity and Sympathy. Informants expressed that they feel: (1) sorry for the clients' condition; (2) sorrow, misery, pain and distress while being with the client; (3) sympathetic and empathic disposition when observing the client.

There are identified disagreements with regards to the issue of sympathy. It is an agreed reality that nurses must empathize and not sympathize (Videbeck, 2008). With sympathy, nurses may project personal concerns which hinder the ability to view the client's needs objectively. However, Travelbee (1964) believed that nursing should be accomplished through human relationships that begin with the original encounter and progress through the stages of emerging identities. This leads to the development of empathy and sympathy which is essential to a successful patient care established with an interactive process: (1) original encounter; (2) visibility of personal or emerging identities; (3) empathy; (4) sympathy; and (5) establishment of mutual understanding and rapport.

Hostility. When clients perform misbehaviors, hostile or aggressive behaviors some informants reported that they feel mad or angry towards the client. In fact some reported to visualize the act of inflicting harm to the clients. This is not new after all - Bailey (1994), Anderson and Standen (2007) and

Patterson and colleagues (2007) identified that most nursing staff dealing with patients with mental health problems were found to hold blaming and hostile attitudes, and were often reported to have treated this client group in a demeaning way. This is thought to be rooted from the fact that they are not equipped or not competent to deal with psychiatric clients.

Charity and Altruism. Since most of the clients were poor, some students assisted by extending help by giving money to the clients and habitually providing amenities. This is failure in the part of the student nurse: the act encourages dependence, wherein fact nurses are expected to promote independence.

Inasmuch as charity and altruism are virtuous, nurses must remember professional boundaries and ethics in practice. This statement is best exemplified in a blog entitled; Nurse Giving Kidney to a Patient is nothing to Celebrate:

"... and this is the exact reason why people in helping professions (doctor, nurse, clergy, social worker, therapist, lawyer, teacher, etc) are schooled on things like 'boundaries' and 'ethics'. These guidelines prohibit behaviors that aren't illegal per se, like engaging in romantic/sexual relationships with clients/patients, giving money to patients/clients, or even providing treatment to relatives or loved ones, but are detrimental or threatening to the professional dynamic. The point is to keep the professional's focus on the job at hand, and to avoid preferential or discriminating behavior..." (Cristy at Living Donor 101 dot com, 2012, January 16).

Ambivalence. This experience by one of the informants is a combination of being overly concerned and being hostile towards the patient. There is a feeling of wanting to help the client and at the same time condemning the client's behavior.

Ambivalent feelings can be eliminated when a well-grounded pre-orientation or the pre-interaction phase of the nurse-client relationship was done. This phase demands personal examination of feelings and preconceptions that may affect the professional relationship with the client, especially when they find the client's experience similar to theirs (Prema, 2006).

Interest and Dating. Some students showed extreme interest by exchanging mobile numbers with the client and dated them. This phenomenon is very dangerous for it may harm both parties: (1) psychiatric client may harm the caregiver; and (2) the client may not be able to adjust with the demands of the relationship. Thus, caregivers are expected to maintain professional boundaries all the time.

"Maintaining professional boundaries is a competency in nursing. The ability to establish and maintain therapeutic boundaries with clients is an essential component of safe, competent, ethical nursing care. Therapeutic relationships are different from social relationships such as friendship or dating. Several nursing competencies relate to the ability to recognize and respect the boundary signs in nurse-client relationships. Registered nurses are expected to: (1) understand and apply the nursing practice standards; (2) interpret the legal requirements of nursing licensure, legislation and scope of practice; (3) avoid personal bias when collecting, interpreting and communicating information about those in their care; (4) promote the client's participation, choice and control in meeting their health-care needs; (5) identify one's own strengths and limitations through self-evaluation; and (6) demonstrate an ethical approach to practice." (College and Association of Registered Nurses of Alberta, 2005)

Researchers' Reflection. Students were observed to display counter-transference masked in different garments. Positive relationship failed to transpire since students were less prepared for psychiatric clinical exposure. Self-awareness strategies need to be comprehensive to facilitate a better nurse-client relationship.

In the Code of Ethics for Filipino Nurses, On Registered Nurses and Patients, when caring for clients, the nurse should respect the individuality and address the totality of every client. The nurse must act as a client's advocate and should maintain professionalism at all times.

It was stated that the nurse should know the definition and scope of nursing practice which are also embodied in the provisions of Republic Act No. 9173, otherwise known as the "Philippine Nursing Act of 2002" and Board Resolution No. 425, Series of 2003, the "Implementing Rules and Regulations of the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002", (IRR RA 9173). Also, the nurse must be aware of their duties and responsibilities in the practice of their profession as embodied in Section 28 of the "Philippine Nursing

Act of 2002" and the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act 9173.

Nurses should bear in mind that the nurse-client relationship entails the therapeutic use of self. To keep it at this level is to have self-awareness. Thus, it is vital to revive the usual practice of utilizing the Gestalt Therapy Technique in promoting self-awareness.

The nurse's role in the therapeutic relationship is theoretically well defined. The client's needs are separated from the nurse's needs, and the client's roles are different from that of the nurse. Therefore, the boundaries of the relationship seem to be well stated. In reality, boundaries are at risk of blurring, and a shift in the nurse-client relationship may lead to nontherapeutic dynamics. Pilette and associates (1995) described the following two common circumstances that can produce blurring of boundaries: (1) when the relationship slips into a social context; and (2) when the nurse's needs are met at the expense of the client's needs (Pilette et al., 1995).

Conclusion

In summary it can be concluded that the nurse or the client can really cross the boundaries of the therapeutic relationship established either transference or counter-transference. Going through the different phases of Peplau's Interpersonal Theory and assuming the different roles of the nurse during the nurse-client relationship, it can be inferred that at any point or any role, transference and counter-transference may strike. Further it can be concluded that the absence of the self-awareness program among students, the phenomenon of counter-transference becomes inevitable. From a variety of reasons triggering the phenomenon, counter-transference was experienced because of having failed to examine and resolve issues in oneself.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers would recommend the following:

1. The pre-orientation phase should not only be applied in Psychiatric ward exposures, because self-awareness is very important in all facets of a student nurses' life.
2. To the Student Nurses, heighten awareness on self, utilizing the Nursing Boundary Index. Be aware also of the phases of the nurse-patient relationship, identifying strategies in order to avoid occurrence of counter-transference.
3. To the future researchers, that this study might serve as an impetus for further studies. The researchers would recommend exploring on the early childhood experiences of those individuals who had experienced countertransference. The researchers would also recommend a quantitative study, identifying the common countertransference reactions among registered nurses.
4. To the Clinical Instructors, a more comprehensive clinical supervision policy will be implemented in order to guide student nurses in their respective Related Learning Experiences.
5. To the proposed guides, using the standard tool that will serve as a comprehensive guide to both student nurses and clinical instructors as well.
6. Revive the Gestalt Therapy Technique as part of the requirements in the subject Psychiatric Nursing as a means of promoting self-awareness prior to clinical exposure.

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In a study conducted by Yang and his co author, *H. verticillata* has been found to contain flavanols. Flavonoids are present in most plants and are basic structures of flavonoid molecules are composed of three rings. They are divided into classes according to their substituent and oxidation state. Common classes and their respective food sources are anthocyanidins (berries, red grapes and red wines), flavones (green leafy vegetables), flavanols (soybeans)²². In nature, they are present principally as glycosides. Sugar moieties are attached to flavonoids increase their solubility. Flavonoids are found in plant cell vacuoles. Flavonoids can function as colorants and seed dispersers, as antioxidants to protect plants from herbivores and host-species recognition, as signal molecules to attract pollinators and defense against bacteria and fungal attack, and as bitter or astringent taste attributes to repel birds and other animals.^{23,24,25}

Figure 1. (a) *H. verticillata* (b) *H. verticillata* (c) *H. verticillata* (d) *H. verticillata* (e) *H. verticillata* (f) *H. verticillata* (g) *H. verticillata* (h) *H. verticillata* (i) *H. verticillata* (j) *H. verticillata* (k) *H. verticillata* (l) *H. verticillata* (m) *H. verticillata* (n) *H. verticillata* (o) *H. verticillata* (p) *H. verticillata* (q) *H. verticillata* (r) *H. verticillata* (s) *H. verticillata* (t) *H. verticillata* (u) *H. verticillata* (v) *H. verticillata* (w) *H. verticillata* (x) *H. verticillata* (y) *H. verticillata* (z) *H. verticillata* (aa) *H. verticillata* (ab) *H. verticillata* (ac) *H. verticillata* (ad) *H. verticillata* (ae) *H. verticillata* (af) *H. verticillata* (ag) *H. verticillata* (ah) *H. verticillata* (ai) *H. verticillata* (aj) *H. verticillata* (ak) *H. verticillata* (al) *H. verticillata* (am) *H. verticillata* (an) *H. verticillata* (ao) *H. verticillata* (ap) *H. verticillata* (aq) *H. verticillata* (ar) *H. verticillata* (as) *H. 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